

ROLE OF BANGLADESH TEA BOARD ON ENHANCING PRODUCTIVITY AND QUALITY OF BANGLADESH TEA

Major General Md. Ashraful Islam, *ndc, psc**

Abstract

Since ancient times, tea has been acknowledged as a health-promoting beverage, and it is one of the most significant non-alcoholic beverages worldwide. In Bangladesh, tea cultivation was started first near the Chittagong Club in the 1840s and Malnicherra Tea Estate in Sylhet is the first tea estate in Bangladesh established in 1854. Tea industry of Bangladesh is one of the key sources of income for the national treasury, accounting for 1% of the nation's GDP. Bangladesh Tea Board is a statutory body, was formed for the development of the tea industry through the Tea Ordinance 1977, which is now functioning by the Tea Act, 2016. There are two institutions under Bangladesh Tea Board: Bangladesh Tea Research Institute (BTRI) and Project Development Unit (PDU). There are about 168 tea estates producing about 102.92 million kg of made tea in 2023, which is a record for the tea history of Bangladesh. However, due to local consumption and other considerations, Bangladesh tea is nearly extinct from traditional worldwide markets. In 1980, 30.98 million kg were exported, accounting for 77.37% of the entire production; by 2023, however, exports accounted for just 1.01% of total tea produced. We used to be a tea exporting country once, but now we import tea since our consumption of tea exceeds our production. A 'Roadmap for Development: Bangladesh Tea Industry' was initiated by Bangladesh Tea Board, including 11 action strategies for the development of the tea industry and to boost production of about 140 million kg by 2025, meeting both domestic consumption and resuming foreign tea exports. Currently, Bangladesh Tea Board is also focusing intensively on research about varietal improvement, modern planting techniques, integrated disease and pest management, modern tea manufacturing technologies, tea export strategies, etc., with proper extension of plantation in different regions of Bangladesh providing sufficient training as well as planting materials and machineries for enhancing productivity and quality of Bangladesh Tea.

Keywords: Bangladesh Tea, Quality, Production, Bangladesh Tea Research Institute, Project Development Unit

Chairman, Bangladesh Tea Board, 171-172 Baizid Bostami Road, Nasirabad, Chattogram.

*Corresponding author's email: chairmanbtb@gmail.com (Major General Md. Ashraful Islam, *ndc, psc*)

Introduction

Due to its enormous economic significance, tea (*Camellia sinensis* (L.) Kuntze, Theaceae) is an important agricultural crop that is produced all over the world (Das et al., 2015 ; Yang et al., 2015). One of the most widely consumed non-alcoholic beverages in the world, tea is becoming more and more well-known as a "health drink" due to its potential medical benefits. Throughout ancient times, tea consumption has been associated with health benefits (Khan and Mukhtar, 2019). Almost two-thirds of people in the entire world have it every morning (Kurahashi et al, 2008).

In Bangladesh, tea was first grown in the 1840s adjacent to the 'Chittagong Club' (Nasir and Shamsuddoha, 2012). The earliest tea estate in Bangladesh was Malnicherra Tea Estate in Sylhet, which was founded in 1854 and began commercial production in 1857 (TTAB, 2024). There are about 168 tea estates producing about 102.92 million kg of made tea in 2023, which is a record of the tea history of Bangladesh (BTB, 2023). Tea industry of Bangladesh is one of the key sources of income for the national treasury, accounting for 1% of the nation's GDP (Raza, 2019). Bangladesh is ranked 8th in terms of production around the world (ITC, 2022).

While tea production reached from 18.36 million kg to 102.918 million kg between 1947 and 2023, tea exports dropped to 96.64% during the past 43 years (from 1980 to 2023). In 1980, 30.98 million kg were exported, accounting for 77.37% of the entire production; by 2023, however, exports accounted for just 1.01% of total tea produced. The primary cause was the exceptionally high level of consumption, which increased as the population and the quantity of tea produced increased.

Currently, Bangladesh tea sector has faced a lot of difficulties. Due to high rainfall, drought, leaching of nutrients and water, crop removal, lack of modern machinery and equipment, lack of capital, lack of skilled manpower, lower market value, low-yielding seedling plants, old plantations, inadequate shade trees, soil and climatic properties, lack of proper irrigation and drainage systems, lack of educational facilities for the labors, discrimination between male and female workers, etc. the production of Bangladesh tea is not adequately stable (Rahman, 2006). Thus, there is an urgent need to strengthen the tea manufacturing industry in Bangladesh, devoting particular attention to the quality, productivity, and cost of tea as well as the marketing system (Islam et al., 2005). The tea industry of Bangladesh may pursue its objectives by implementing intensive plantations that include elite clones and seed stocks. However, as there is no additional land available for expanding the tea plantation, it is necessary to enhance the current areas by introducing high-yield and high-quality clones. By filling vacancies and planting new improved clones in areas where old tea plants have been discarded, tea production may be increased towards the intended objectives, making the old tea estates economically viable. So, tea planters should prioritize the use of enhanced cultivars that meet the industry's needs (Palni et al., 1999).

Bangladesh Tea Board is a statutory body which was formed for the development of tea industry. In 1977, Tea Ordinance-1959 was repealed and Tea Ordinance-1977 was issued and Bangladesh Tea Board was established under this Ordinance. Bangladesh Tea Board is being managed as per the Tea Act, 2016. There are two institutions under Bangladesh Tea Board are: Bangladesh Tea Research Institute (BTRI) and Project Development Unit (PDU). The main aim of Bangladesh Tea Research Institute is to increase productivity and quality through scientific research, to provide science-based advice and support in the development and excellence of the tea industry, and to spread the latest technology in the tea industry. On the other hand, the main mission of Project Development Unit (PDU) is to maximize tea production & quality by utilizing whole tea cultivable land in Bangladesh, motivating small holding tea cultivation and exporting tea after meeting our local demand (BTB, 2024; BTRI, 2024 and PDU, 2024). Bangladesh Tea Board is now focusing intensively on research about varietal improvement, modern planting techniques, integrated disease and pest management, modern tea manufacturing technologies, tea export strategies etc., with the proper extension of plantation in different regions of Bangladesh providing sufficient training as well as planting materials and machinery for enhancing productivity and quality of Bangladesh Tea.

History of Bangladesh Tea Industry

In the early 1800s, tea cultivation began in Assam and adjacent areas of India. Tea cultivation began in Bangladesh in the early 1840s. The early history of tea in Bangladesh is the history of tea in Northeast India, particularly the history of Surma Valley. The period 1827-1857 is very significant as the beginning of tea cultivation in the subcontinent, especially for Bangladesh. The latter part of this period saw the expansion of tea cultivation in the greater Sylhet and greater Chittagong districts of Bangladesh. Tea cultivation started in Chittagong in 1839-40 (Ahmed, 2021; Mamun, 2019).

The tea plants were mainly seeded hybrids, but there were also some local Assamese and China type tea plants. In 1840, District Collector Mr. Scones first collected some tea seeds from Assam and some Chinese type tea plants from the Kolkata Botanical Garden and planted them in front of the Chittagong Club, known as 'Kunduder Bagan'. Chittagong's first tea garden was the 'Pioneer' indeed. But unfortunately, this tea-cultivation initiative did not survive. Another gentleman Mr. Hogg, personally cultivates an acre or two of tea in spades across the Karnaphuli River. This was the second attempt at tea cultivation. Finally, the first tea was prepared in Chittagong in 1843. Meanwhile, remarkable progress has been made in Assam. The presence of local tea plants in the Chandkhani hills of Sylhet was found in 1855 (Ahmed, 1963).

In the same year, tea cultivation began in the Surma Valley comprising various districts of Cachar and Sylhet. A few years later, tea plants were discovered in their natural state in the Khasia and Jaintia hills bordering Sylhet district. Then in 1854, Malanichhara tea plantation was established near Airport Road in Sylhet city in 1847. Originally, Malnichrai was the first commercial tea garden in Bangladesh. Formerly, the tea sector in Bangladesh was closely linked to the tea production in North East India. As a result, the Tocklai Experimental Station of India provided scientific assistance to the tea industry in Bangladesh (Alam, 1992).

Post-Partition 1947

Prior to the partition and until 1947, teas made in the Sylhet and Surmah valleys were referred to be Indian teas, but were also recognized as Sweet liquoring Surmah valley teas. All the teas were produced using the Orthodox method, and their quality was very close to that of teas from the nearby Cachar area. There was apparently limited Legg-Cut and green tea manufacturing prior to 1947. Towards the end of the 19th century, the expansion of tea business concentrated towards the establishment of various Limited liability companies such as M/S Duncan Brothers & Co. Ltd., James Finlay & Co. and Octovious Steel & Co. Ltd., M/S Macneill & Co. Ltd. By 1903, there were 15 European planters in North Sylhet, 102 in South Sylhet (Moulvibazar) and 26 in Hobigonj region of larger Sylhet (Mamun, 2011).

Post-Partition 1947-1971

After partition, the subcontinent was basically divided into two political territories - India and Pakistan (comprising West and East Pakistan) (Ferdous, 2021). There were 133 tea estates in Pakistan in 1947 when it gained its independence. By 1971, this number had increased to 147, representing around 90,000 workers out of the 249,000 people that resided across the nation (Hossain, 2018).

The 1971 War of Liberation

The tea sector faced several challenges in 1971 during the War of Liberation. Along with the destruction to several factories, two-thirds of the veteran planters of British and Pakistani descent abandoned the business while many senior Bangladeshi planters served in the war. This implied that the estates were being managed by unskilled individuals who had to deal with unsettling circumstances. In fact, several of the battling happened just next to the borders, in the tea garden regions. The bungalow of the manager of 'Teliapara Tea Estate' served as the first place of assembly for the senior officers of the Eastern Sector of the Liberation War after the crackdown on April 4, 1971. This bungalow later served as the headquarters of the Bangladesh Forces Headquarters (BDFHQ) for a considerable amount of time (Bhuyan, 2014).

After 1971, War of Liberation

Right after the war, England was a readily accessible source of support. In 1973, the British organization Overseas Development Administration (ODA), at the insistence of the Government of Bangladesh, assigned the Commonwealth Development Corporation (CDC) with evaluating the prerequisites for a process of revitalization and restructuring the tea sector, including tea growing, manufacture, research, markets and market organization, with an assessment of the financial and economic returns to such a program. Furthermore, the government-backed Dastagir Committee, which investigated the financial limitations of many estates, offered its suggestions in 1976; they turned out to be very successful. The Bangladesh Tea Board was reformed in 1977 with goals similar to those of the previous Pakistan Tea Board, which had been established by the Pakistan Tea Act of 1950. The Tea Board's role as oversight across Bangladesh's tea industry has grown to include crop monitoring and disposal, export license issuance to buyers, permission to permit producers to sell directly to consumers and consignment, among other things.

The Tea Traders Association of Pakistan was replaced in 1974 by the Tea Traders Association of Bangladesh. After eight years, the imperial method of weight was replaced with the metric system for tea marketing. During 1975-76, in an attempt to increase yields, the Tea Board prepared two plans for intensive cultivation and replanting. Bangladesh Tea Research Institute BTRI, the scientific wing of the Tea Board, also brought out several high yielding clonal varieties of distinct character and quality (Mondal et al., 2004; Muthaiya et al., 2013 and Li et al., 2015).

By 1979, British experts had devised a plan to revive Bangladesh's embattled tea sector. While there was already a scheme in place for the intense cultivation and replanting of tea at this point, the most significant effort began in 1983-84 and went into action in 1985-86. Throughout this time, CTC (Crush-Tear-Curl) teas gained popularity in Bangladesh among domestic and foreign consumers because to its ability to produce more robust faster-brewing liquor with more cuppage. Almost 99 percent of the tea types produced in Bangladesh now are CTC teas (Islam et al., 2021 and Hossain, 2015).

Bangladesh Tea Board

Bangladesh Tea Board is a statutory body. The then Pakistan Tea Board was formed on February 22, 1951 under the Pakistan Tea Act-1950. Father of the Nation Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman served as the chairman of the then Tea Board from 04 June 1957 to 23 October 1958. On August 8, 1959, the Tea Ordinance 1959 was issued to regulate the Tea Board by repealing the Pakistan Tea Act-1950.

In 1977, Tea Ordinance-1959 was repealed and Tea Ordinance-1977 was issued and Bangladesh Tea Board was established under this Ordinance. On August 1, 2016, through a gazette, the Government repealed the Tea Ordinance-1977 and promulgated the Tea Act, 2016. Bangladesh Tea Board is being managed as per the Tea Act, 2016. There are two institutions under Bangladesh Tea Board are: Bangladesh Tea Research Institute (BTRI) and Project Development Unit (PDU).

Regulatory Body of Bangladesh Tea Board

Bangladesh Tea Board comprises of following members:

1. Honorable Chairman, Bangladesh Tea Board
2. Member (Research & Development) and Member (Finance & Trade)
3. Divisional Commissioner of Chittagong, Sylhet and Rangpur
4. Joint secretary, Ministry of Commerce

5. Joint secretary, Ministry of Land
6. Chief Forest Conservator, Forest Department
7. Chairman, Bangladesh Tea Association
8. Chairman, Tea Traders Association of Bangladesh
9. One (01) Member from Tea Brokers, Appointed by the Government of Bangladesh
10. Two (02) Members from Tea Planters, Appointed by the Government of Bangladesh

Functions of Bangladesh Tea Board

The main activities of Bangladesh Tea Board are development of tea industry and taking all measures to increase production, marketing and export of tea, establishment of new tea plantations and rehabilitation of abandoned tea plantations, imposition of sub-tax on tea produced in Bangladesh and taking measures in other related matters and overall tea Regulating the activities of industry. The vision and mission of Bangladesh Tea Board are following;

Vision: To grow more quality tea to serve greater demand; i.e. grow for export after meeting our local demand.

Mission: To maximize tea production & quality by utilizing whole tea cultivable land in Bangladesh, motivating small holding tea cultivation and exporting tea after meeting our local demand.

According to Tea Act, 2016 the functions of the Board are given below:

- i. Adopting suitable actions to promote the overall development of the tea industry;
- ii. Implementing strategies to enhance tea yield;
- iii. Control and management of import, export and sale of tea;
- iv. Evaluating the quality of different types of tea and taking measures to improve the quality of tea;
- v. Taking arrangements for tea tasting training;
- vi. Collection of information from tea producers, manufacturers or traders or any other person associated with tea and tea industry;
- vii. To undertake and conduct scientific, technical and economically viable research activities on tea cultivation technology as well as to establish and maintain demonstration fields for increasing the production and quality of tea.;
- viii. Aid in the control of insects and pests harmful to tea;
- ix. Providing necessary support for the growth of cooperative activities among small garden tea producers;
- x. Training arrangements for persons engaged in tea cultivation and garden management and employees working under the control of the Board;
- xi. Undertake scientific, technical and economic research activities and provide necessary assistance in maintenance of demonstration farms and production centers for increasing production of tea and other cash crops.;
- xii. Collection and conservation of information from tea producers, manufacturers or traders or any other person associated with tea for the betterment of tea industry;
- xiii. Registration of tea estates and factories as well as licensing of estate owners, tea manufacturers, exporters, blenders, bidders, brokers, tea waste dealers and wholesalers with retailers;
- xiv. To take charge of any business or to acquire, take over or operate any business establishment as directed by the Government;
- xv. Establishment of new plantations including taking over and rehabilitating abandoned plantations as per the plan approved by the Government and generally providing necessary support to the existing plantations to increase production;
- xvi. Taking appropriate measures to ensure utilization of surplus land of tea estates;

- xvii. Adoption of welfare measures for plantation workers and employees and
- xviii. To take appropriate measures and undertake other activities as directed by the Government from time to time for the development of tea industry in Bangladesh (Tea Act, 2016).

Present Status of Bangladesh Tea

Table 01 represents tea production (million kg), consumption (million kg), export (million kg) and export value from 1947 to 2023 (BTB, 2023; Mondal et al., 2021; Ahmad et al., 2013; Arefin and Hossain 2022). Tea exports have dropped to 96.64% during the past 43 years (from 1980 to 2023), despite a 460.55% improvement in production from 1947 to 2023. In 1980, the share of tea exported was 77.37% of the entire production; by 2023, however, currently it was just 1.01%. The primary cause was the high rate of quick consumption, which increased as the population and tea production. A significant correlation was found to exist between the production, consumption, and export of tea. The correlation coefficient or r value, between tea production and consumption is 0.95, which indicates a significant positive relationship and shows that our consumption of tea is rising daily in tandem with production. However, a significant negative correlation (r value = -0.74) was identified between tea consumption and export, indicating that our intensive tea drinking habit has over time led to a decline in export.

Table 1. Tea Production (Million Kg), Consumption (Million Kg), Export (Million Kg) and Export Value (M. BDT) from 1947-2023 in Bangladesh.

Year	Production (Million Kg)	Consumption (Million Kg)	Export (Million Kg)	Export Value (M. BDT)
1947	18.36	-	-	-
1970	28.00	5.77	-	-
1980	40.04	9.06	30.98	-
1990	45.89	14.21	26.45	-
2001	53.15	36.95	12.92	894.99
2002	53.62	41.5	13.65	939.93
2003	58.3	37.44	12.18	915.07
2004	56	43.33	13.11	934.04
2005	60.14	43.3	9.01	742.62
2006	53.41	40.51	4.79	469.59
2007	58.19	46.27	10.56	899.01
2008	58.66	52.12	8.39	976.95
2009	59.99	53.74	3.16	433.5
2010	60.04	57.63	0.91	176.68
2011	59.13	58.5	1.48	213.51
2012	62.52	61.19	1.56	222.28
2013	66.26	64	0.54	133.04
2014	63.88	67.17	2.66	281.72
2015	67.38	77.57	0.54	105.13
2016	85.05	81.64	0.62	140.56
2017	78.95	85.93	2.56	377.29
2018	82.13	90.45	0.65	203.93
2019	96.07	95.2	0.6	194.26
2020	86.39	91.97 (calculated)	2.17	347.14
2021	96.506	95.2 (calculated)	0.68	180.57
2022	93.829	98.43 (calculated)	0.78	196.31
2023	102.918	101.65 (calculated)	1.04	272.52

Tea production, consumption and export of Bangladesh of last two decades were presented in Fig. 1. The production and consumption were found to be upward trending while export was found declining over time. The regression equation of tea production, consumption and export were $y = 0.1231x^2 - 0.7736x + 56.252$, $y = 0.0554x^2 + 1.8972x + 32.98$ and $y = 0.0491x^2 - 1.782x + 16.696$ respectively. From the regression equation of tea production, it can be calculated that the production will be 113.85 million kg by 2025 and 143.83 million kg by 2030.

Fig. 1. Tea production, consumption and export of Tea from 2001-2023 with regression equation

In Bangladesh, there are 167 tea estates in Moulvibazar, Habiganj, Sylhet, Chattogram, Rangamati, Panchagarh, Thakurgaon and khagrachari district. District wise number of tea estates was provided in Fig. 02. At present, Moulvibazar district (90) has the highest number of tea gardens in the country. Besides, there are 25 tea gardens in Habiganj, district, 22 in Chattogram, 19 in Sylhet, 8 in Panchagarh, 2 in Rangamati, 1 in Thakurgaon and 1 tea garden is situated in khagrachari district. Recently, the highest tea production was recorded in the history of 184 years of Bangladesh tea industry. A total of 102.92 million kg of tea has been produced in 2023 from 168 tea gardens and small scale tea gardens in the country, surpassing all previous records of tea production.

Fig. 2. Major tea growing districts with number of tea garden in Bangladesh

Tea cultivation in Northern Region of Bangladesh

Panchagarh is the pioneer district of small-scale tea cultivation in the northern region of Bangladesh. After Greater Chittagong and Sylhet, North Bengal is already known as the third tea region of the country. Tea cultivation in northern region is the brainchild of Hon'ble Prime Minister. In 1996, the then and current Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina visited Panchagarh district and thought about the potential of tea cultivation. According to the command, tea cultivation was carried out experimentally under supervision of the Deputy Commissioner of that time Mr. Md. Rabiul Islam. In 1999, tea cultivation plan was adopted in North Bengal. In October 1999, an expert team of Bangladesh Tea Board conducted a survey in Panchagarh and Thakurgaon districts to ascertain the potential of tea cultivation. The survey committee determined the potential for tea cultivation on about 40,000 acres of land in Panchagarh and Thakurgaon districts. Later in 2000 Tetulia Tea Company Limited (TTCL, 2000) and Kazi & Kazi Tea Garden started commercial tea cultivation. At that time, 6-7 small farmers started tea cultivation with the advice of Bangladesh Tea Board officials. Since then, tea cultivation in North Bengal gradually gained wide spread, trust and popularity. The overall scenario of tea (both tea cultivated land and made tea production) in North Bengal from the beginning to last year (2023) is presented through Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. A record amount of 17.93 million kg of tea has been added to the national production in 2023 from the plain tea plantations and small scale plantations in the northern region which is 17.42% of total national production (Barua, 2024; Mamun, 2022; Ahmed, 2015; Ahmed, 2014)

Fig. 3. Tea cultivation (thousand acre) in Northern region of Bangladesh

Fig. 4. Made Tea production (million Kg) in Northern region of Bangladesh

Role of improved planting materials in upgrading production and quality of tea industry

In comparison with other tea-growing nations around the world, our current production per hectare is rather low (Aziz et al., 2020). Approximately 35% of our tea producing area is made up of older and less productive seedling plants that are over 60 years old, which is one of the main causes of lower production of Bangladesh (PDU, 2015). Tea exports diminish as a result of rising domestic consumption decreasing exportable surplus and a slow pace of production growth. The tea sector has experienced a minimal economic return due to unfavorable weather circumstances and rising production costs. Under these conditions, the industry must expand in new areas and replant existing ones using higher-yielding and better-quality planting materials (Dutta and Alam, 2001). Therefore, by providing long-term employment opportunities for marginal landowners and the large landless population, as well as by optimizing the commercial use of fallow land in a land-hungry nation like Bangladesh, the development and cultivation of new, high-yielding tea varieties can contribute to the eradication of poverty (Hossain et al., 2017).

Superior planting materials with desired traits can be developed by hybridizing within existing genetic diversity or by introducing new genetic variability through other non-conventional breeding techniques such polyploidy, mutation, and tissue culture. The conventional methods of tea crop improvement are i) introduction, ii) selection, and ii) hybridization. Since its founding, BTRI has prioritized clonal selection and hybridization programs with the goal of developing planting materials with high yield and quality potential. The institution has provided 23 Vegetative Clones and 5 Bi-clone Seedling (Seed Stock) in the BT-series to the industry so far, as a result of these researches (Table 02).

Table 2. BTRI released Clones and Bi-Clone Seedlings with their yield and quality

Clone/ Bi-Clone Seedling	Release Year	Yield (Kg/ha) At Mature Stage	Quality*	Category**
BT1	1966	3298	AA	Standard
BT2	1975	3627	AA	Standard
BT3	1975	3431	AA	Standard
BT4	1981	2581	E	Quality
BT5	1987	2811	AA	Standard
BT6	1987	2916	E	Quality
BT7	1991	2790	AA	Standard
BT8	1992	3316	AA	Standard
BT9	1994	3784	AA	Standard
BT10	1995	4600	AA	Yield
BT11	1999	3713	AA	Standard
BT12	2000	4018	AA	Yield
BT13	2000	3203	AA	Standard
BT14	2002	3450	AA	Standard
BT15	2002	3735	E	Quality
BT16	2005	3604	AA	Standard
BT17	2006	3897	AA	Standard
BT18	2010	3777	AA	Standard
BT19	2016	3877	AA*F	Standard
BT20	2016	3685	E	Quality
BT21	2018	3447	AA	Standard
BT22	2021	3304.15	E	Quality
BT23	2021	3341.75	AA	Standard (DT)
BTS1	1985	3217	AA	-----
BTS2	1985	3110	AA	-----
BTS3	2001	3381	AA	-----
BTS4	2001	3303	AA	-----
BTS5	2019	3709.9	AA	-----

Note:

* Quality category based on Tea Quality score:

- i. E = Excellent (≤ 34 out of 50)
- ii. AA = Above Average ($32 \leq$ to < 34 out of 50)
- iii. A = Average ($30 \leq$ to < 32 out of 50)
- iv. BA = Below Average (< 30 out of 50) (Bezbaruah and Dutta, 1977)

** Clonal category based on Yield Quality:

- i. Yield clone: Yield of ≥ 4000 Kg/ha with Above average or Average Cup Quality,
- ii. Standard clone: Yield of $3000 - < 4000$ Kg/ha with Above Average or Average Cup Quality,
- iii. Quality clone: Yield of $2500 - < 3000$ Kg/ha with Excellent Cup Quality (Amma, 1974; Bezbaruah and Dutta, 1977; Wachira, 1994)

The first vegetative clone of BTRI, named Bangladesh Tea 1 (BT1), was developed in 1966. The tea industry suffered greatly during the 1971 liberation war and production was significantly impacted. The usage of BTRI-released clones was steadily extended after 1971 in order to boost up Bangladesh Tea yield and quality. From the Fig. 5, it was observed that the clonal adaptation and tea production was increased from early 1980. According to a research conducted in 1994, 90% of the whole tea area was occupied by seedlings, with the remaining clones being mostly garden clones and a small amount of imported clones (Alam, 1994). A positive change in the clonal plantation was seen in the subsequent 2001 investigation. That research examined 58.72% of the entire tea area, of which 21.02% were pure clonal plantations, 3.6% were bi- and polyclonal seedlings and the remaining plantations were general seedlings (Alam, 2002). According to a different study, the average area of entire tea plantation is 54.34% for seedlings and 41.64% for clones (Boonerjee, 2016). The Statistics Division of BTRI recently carried out an experiment in which the adoption rates of TV and BT clones in the 144 tea estates spread across several valleys were investigated. The experiment revealed that clonal plantations with an average productivity of 1607.48 kg/ha, occupied around 41.64% of the total tea areas of the seven valleys. The percentage of Indian TV clones and Bangladeshi clones usage was about 40.20% and 45.05%, respectively (BTRI, 2020). Furthermore, a noteworthy relationship has been noticed between tea production and the rate of clonal adaptability in Bangladesh. There is a significant positive association between tea production and the rate of clonal adaptability, as indicated by the correlation coefficient ($r = +0.98$).

Fig 5. Increasing Rate of Clonal Adaptation and Tea Production of Bangladesh (1980-2020)

Some Recent activities of Bangladesh Tea Board in Research, Development and Finance of Bangladesh Tea Industry

- i. Research and sustainable technologies were developed by BTRI for the betterment of tea industry such as innovation and application of organic fertilizer and vermicompost production technology, determination of poultry manure ingredients, development of high yielding, quality and drought tolerant varieties of tea, determining ideal planting technique for tea plantations in Bangladesh, controlling pests of tea (such as *Helopeltis*, red spider, nematodes etc.), developing Integrated Pest Management (IPM) strategies, determination of pesticide residues in prepared tea, integrated management in suppression of tea diseases (horsehair blight, red rust, gall, charcoal stump rot, root rot diseases etc), BTRI developed techniques for determination of biochemical properties of TF, TR and other components of free clones and forecasting of annual production of tea crops.
- ii. On the birth centenary of Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman, the greatest Bengali of all time and the Father of the Nation, under the initiative of the Ministry of Agriculture, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Council (BARC) has published '100 Agricultural Technology Atlas'. The '100 Agricultural Technology Atlas' was unveiled by the Honorable Prime Minister of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, Sheikh Hasina, MP. The book featured 4 technologies developed by Bangladesh Tea Research Institute such as 'Improved variety clone BT2', 'Seed variety BTS1', 'IPM technology for sustainable tea production' and 'Use of green crops to improve soil quality'.
- iii. Tea industry stakeholders are regularly informed about institute research findings and sustainable technologies developed. Technology transfer activities are conducted through advisory tours, research sub-committees, annual courses, seminars, workshops, annual reports, journals, circulars, notifications, letters, pamphlets, tea tasting sessions, emails, websites, electronic media and mobile apps. Recently Bangladesh Tea Board has developed several mobile apps named 'Duti Pata Ekti Kuri', 'Cha Seba', 'Somotoler Cha Shilpo', 'Bangladesh Tea Industry', 'Tea soft' for the successful technology transfer and for the betterment of tea planters.
- iv. According to the Tea Act-2016, inspection and evaluation of the development activities of tea plantations in Bangladesh, inspection of tea factory, on-site inspection and report preparation of tea plantation expansion at the rate of 2.5% have been conducted by Project Development Unit (PDU), an organ of the Bangladesh Tea Board. Besides, Hands-on training workshops for skill development of tea estate managers and timely training workshops for Tila Babu of tea estates and small tea farmers of North Bengal have organized for quality tea production. Professional Diploma in Tea Management (PDTM) for Tea Estate Managers and Assistant Managers and Tea Production Course (TPC) for skill development of gardeners have organized through Management Training Center of PDU (PDU, 2023). Bangladesh Tea Research institute (BTRI) organizes 06 days long 'BTRI Annual Course' every year for tea plantation management and manual training in scientific method for tea growers. 965 tea planters have been trained so far with great success (PDU). In 2022, for the first time, the 'Tea Testing and Quality Control' course was launched by Bangladesh Tea Board.
- v. 'Camellia Khola Akash School' has been launched at union level without walls and roof to deliver training services to the doorsteps of the small tea farmers in the northern region, keeping the slogan 'Improved knowledge, improved tea' in front. Under this programme, more than 100 hands-on training workshops on "Scientific Tea Plantation Management" have been organized for more than 5,000 small tea growers at the union level.

- vi. The short term (2016-2020) target of “Development Roadmap: Bangladesh Tea Industry” for tea industry development has already been implemented. 100% of short term target achieved. Besides, the implementation of the medium term (2021-2025) and long term (2026-2030) targets is ongoing. Incentive of Tk 120.00 crore by Bangladesh Bank was financed at Bangladesh tea industry due to Corona epidemic. [Tea Act, 2016](#) was published as Gazette in schedule of Mobile Courts Act, 2009 for the development of tea industry.
- vii. In order to strengthen research on tea in Chittagong region, 'Bangladesh Tea Research Institute Region Based Tea Research Farm, Banshkhali, Chittagong' was established. A 'Modern Soil Science Laboratory' was established for the first time at BTRI Fatikchari sub-station to analyze soil samples of tea plantations in Chittagong region. Permanent office of Tea Board at Lalmonirhat was also established to strengthen the activity of Bangladesh Tea Board in Northern Region of Bangladesh.
- viii. On March 15, 2021, Chittagong Tea Auction Center launched an online tea auction program on an experimental basis. On December 8, 2017, the country's second tea auction center was launched at Srimangal, Moulvibazar. The country's third tea auction center was launched in Panchagarh in a bid to ensure fair price of tea from bought tea leaves. 'Online Tea License System' was launched for receiving tea license applications online and issuing licenses. The auction price of tea has been set in 'Base Price' line to control the decline in tea prices in recent times for being compatible with the cost of production.
- ix. There is no alternative to export of tea to ensure fair selling price against the bumper yield of tea in the country. Bangladesh Tea Board is working extensively to bring back the lost glory days of tea export. As part of this, recently Bangladesh Tea Board has already exported high-quality orthodox tea to a well-known organization called London Tea Exchange. Bangladesh Tea Board participated in 'Gulfood 2024' held on February 19-23, 2024 in Dubai, United Arab Emirates with the aim of introducing the country's tea industry to the international market and increasing tea exports.
- x. Every year numerous planting materials, irrigation equipment, plucking machines, besides other technologies are distributed among the tea stakeholders at minimal cost and even free of cost to encourage tea growers to adopt modern technology.

Target of Development: Projection upto 2030

A 'Roadmap for Development: Bangladesh Tea Industry' or 'Unnoyoner Pathonoksha: Bangladesh Cha Shilpo' was developed including 11 action strategies for the development of Bangladesh tea industry; which was approved by the Cabinet Division on January 31, 2017 ([BTB, 2016](#)). As part of the Bangladesh Tea Board's plan, it is projected that overall tea output would reach 140 million kg by 2025, meeting both domestic consumption and resuming foreign tea exports ([Ahmed and Ahmed, 2015](#)). Intensive plantations using improved clones and seed stocks are one of the greatest ways to assist tea companies to reach their objectives. However, because additional land is not available for the expansion of tea production, the plantation areas that are now existing must be upgraded with high-yielding, high-quality clones as well as superior seed stock. It is possible to move tea production toward the intended target and keep the existing tea estates financially viable by filling up vacant areas and planting new, better clones and seedstock in previously uprooted regions. Some major strategies of action plan (for developing tea estates, for less developed/sick tea estates, for small holding tea, for BTRI and for PDU) for increasing productivity and quality of Bangladesh Tea are given in Table 3 (a,b,c,d and e).

Table 3.a. Some major action plans for 'Developing Tea Estates' to increase productivity and quality by 2030

Plans	2016-2025			2016-2030		
	Activities	Result		Activities	Result	
Infilling of tea vacant area by 165 lac saplings	Infilling of vacant area by 140 lac tea saplings to reduce tea vacancy 7.00%	Production increase 3.2 million kg	will increase	Infilling of vacant area by total 140+25=165 lac tea saplings to reduce tea vacancy 5.00%	Production will increase 4.8 million kg	
Replanting/ Block Infilling of total 10,000 ha	Replanting/ Block Infilling of total 8,274 ha	Production increase 20 million kg	will increase	Replanting/ Block Infilling of total 8,274+1726=10,000 ha	Production will increase 20+10=30 million kg	
Extension of Tea in new 5,868 ha area	Tea Extension in new 3,868 ha area	Production increase 10 million kg	will increase	Tea Extension in total 3,868+2000=5,868 ha area	Production will increase 10+05=15 million kg	

Table 3.b. Some major action plans for 'Less Developed/ Sick Tea Estates' to increase productivity and quality by 2030

Plans	2016-2025			2016-2030		
	Activities	Result		Activities	Result	
Infilling of tea vacant area by 90 lac saplings	Infilling of vacant area by 70 lac tea saplings to reduce tea vacancy 7.00%	Production increase 0.18 million kg	will increase	Infilling of vacant area by total 70+20=90 lac tea saplings to reduce tea vacancy 5.00%	Production will increase 2.7 million kg	
Replanting/ Block Infilling of total 320 ha	Replanting/ Block Infilling of total 300 ha	Production increase 0.30 million kg	will increase	Replanting/ Block Infilling of total 300+20=320 ha	Production will increase 0.30+0.02=0.32 million kg	
Extension of Tea in new 1,000 ha area	Tea Extension in new 800 ha area	Production increase 1.92 million kg	will increase	Tea Extension in total 800+200=1,000 ha area	Production will increase 1.92+0.48=2.40 million kg	

Table 3.c. Some major action plans for 'Small Holding Tea' to increase productivity and quality by 2030

Plans	2016-2025			2016-2030		
	Activities	Result		Activities	Result	
Extension of Tea in new 4,000 ha area	Tea Extension in new 3500 ha area	Production increase 8.4 million kg	will increase	Tea Extension in total 3500+500=4,000 ha area	Production will increase 8.4+1.2=9.60 million kg	
Establishment of Bought Leaf Factory	New 4 Bought Leaf Factories will be established	8.4 million kg tea will be manufactured by 4 factories	made will be	5 (4+1) Bought Leaf Factories will be established	9.6 million kg tea will be manufactured by 5 factories	

Table 3.d. Some major action plans for enhancing research activities in 'Bangladesh Tea Research Institute (BTRI)' by 2030

Plans	2016-2025	2016-2030
Strengthening of BTRI substations	Strengthening of BTRI substations by funding of 96 lac tk. to disseminate newly developed technologies to the end users	Strengthening of BTRI substations by funding of 126 lac tk. to disseminate newly developed technologies to the end users
Distribution of improved planting materials and other technologies	Funding of 23 lac tk. for the Distribution of improved planting materials and other technologies	Funding of 30 lac tk. for the Distribution of improved planting materials and other technologies
Crop improvement programme	Funding of 8.7 lac tk. for crop improvement programme	Funding of 10.7 lac tk. for crop improvement programme
Tissue culture lab	Adopt the technology for tissue culture for successful root and shoot regeneration	Establishment of tissue culture lab with proper technology for rapid multiplication of tea saplings.
Integrated pest and disease management technology	Funding of 96.2 lac tk. for Integrated pest and disease management technology to control pest and disease of tea gardens	Funding of 103.45 lac tk. for Integrated pest and disease management technology to control pest and disease of tea gardens

Table 3.e. Some major action plans for providing training facilities by 'Project Development Unit (PDU) by 2030

Plans	2016-2025	2016-2030
Postgraduate Diploma Course	Skilled human resource development by Postgraduate Diploma Course of 480 personnel	Skilled human resource development by Postgraduate Diploma Course of 720 personnel
Tea production course	Providing training to 120 tea estate stuffs by Tea production course	Providing training to 180 tea estate stuffs by Tea production course

Conclusion

Tea industry of Bangladesh is a significant labor-intensive, agro-based sector focused on exports. It generates employment, regulates commerce and provides exports, all of which are extremely important to our economy. Currently, however, the tea sector in Bangladesh is dealing with a number of difficulties. Due to local consumption and other considerations, Bangladesh tea is nearly extinct from the traditional worldwide markets. We used to be a tea exporting country, but now we import tea since our consumption of tea exceeds our production. It is highly advised to develop a thorough long-term development strategy for sustainable tea business based on meticulous, scientific, and rigorous study in order to address this issue. Efficient technology transfer system and its proper execution in the field are equally important. The tea industry needs to harness full potential of the innovated technologies developed by BTRI as well as Bangladesh Tea Board to overcome the constraints confronting our tea industry.

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